

doi:10.5281/zenodo.16751443

USA - Taliban Agreement and Peace in Afghanistan

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ABSTRACT

The study have investigated efficacy the peace deal under the Trump's administration and its capacity to engender peace in Afghanistan. The study developed three specific objectives which are to: evaluate the capacity of the deal to engender peace and stability in Afghanistan; examine the challenges facing the deal and recommend other options to peace in Afghanistan. These objectives were used to developed three research questions and three hypotheses. The study was restricted to the 2020 peace agreement between the United States government and the Afghan-Taliban leaders. The variables of interest in the study are armed conflict, peace building in Afghanistan, the challenges to the peace agreement and strategies for peace and stability in Afghanistan. The theoretical framework is hinged on the hegemonic stability theory. The survey research design was employed and anchored on the content analysis for data analysis. The results showed that the USA-Taliban deal does not have the capacity to bring peace and stability in Afghanistan; the absence of Afghan government from the peace negotiation is the cause of her loss of legitimacy and powers; and United Nation as a neutral entity cannot take the responsibility of Afghan peace process. It was thus concluded that the peace deal between the US and Taliban brought a mixed picture wherein the US-Taliban peace deal met a relative success while the intra-Afghan failed as a result of complication in the process, and number of prisoners to release, the system of governance to implement in Afghanistan and the level of reduction on violence by the Taliban were areas of disagreement that marred the intra-Afghan peace talks and eventually led to continued war to saw to the fall of the government to the Taliban following the withdrawal of international assistance. The Deal exposed the Afghan government to helpless attacks and lost of the war and this erodes the ever sought peace and stability. The study made some recommendations among which are that the interest of the Masses should be accommodated in peace deals that aims to bring lasting peace and stability; and that parties that share vested and pecuniary interests in crises should not be part to the truce. This work contributed in the study of the Afghanistan, USA and Taliban crises by examining some unique aspects of the strategies to bringing peace and stability to Afghanistan, that targeted to appreciate the interest of the US government in ending the war and the extent to which the truce accommodated the interest of the Afghan people, the obstacles to the process and the capacity of the United Nations as options to peace accord in Afghanistan.

Keywords: USA, Taliban Agreement, Peace in Afghanistan

INTRODUCTION

The decade long Afghan war began after the September 11, 2001 bombing of the World Trade Centre and a section of the Pentagon. Investigation showed that the al-Qaeda was responsible for hatching and executing the terrorist act along with several other individuals who hijacked four passenger airliners bound for California. Further investigation revealed that these 19 hijackers all received training at an al-

Qaeda base in Afghanistan (Idigo, 2025). As a result of the attack, the administration of the U.S President – George W. Bush, developed a strategy that sought to first remove the Taliban from Afghanistan, and dismantle and capture leading heads of the al-Qaeda terrorist group. President Bush had earlier demanded that the Taliban leader Mullah Mohammed Omar deliver to the United States authorities all the leaders of al-Qaeda who hide in the land and also extradite Osama Bin Laden, a request Mullah Mohammed Omar refused to assent to (Chaudhuri, & Shende, 2020). Hence, the United States – Afghanistan War.

The Bush administration adopted a strategy to “kill and capture” the Taliban and Al Qaeda leaders. However, due to the increase of the insurgency after 2004, the Bush administration changed its Afghanistan war strategy to a state-building strategy (Idigo, 2022). This strategy also proved to be problematic for a number of reasons: first, the Afghan leadership was inexperienced in democratic national governance, which created a hurdle to implementing a representative system by a fair election (Niland 2014); secondly, the U.S. and other Western countries’ focus was on the development of Kabul and other large cities in Afghanistan to make these cities an economic and political model for rural areas. However, this lack of attention to rural areas created the conditions for a resurgence of the Taliban that has challenged governmental control in vast areas of the country (Asey, 2019).

When Barack Obama was elected the President of the United States, he ordered a policy review to replace the phrase global “War on Terror” with “Countering Violent Extremism” (Jenkins, 2017). Operationally, there were few differences between the two policies when they came to be applied on-the-ground. President Obama was sceptical about the efficiency of the US military’s approach to counterinsurgency in Afghanistan under the Bush administration (Landler, 2017). This was at a time when Taliban attacks had spread to 33 out of 34 Afghan provinces. The Taliban’s suicide bomber attacks were becoming increasingly frequent in the capital, Kabul, and in other important city centres. Obama’s new approach was to use intra-agency approach to address the socio-economic problems of Afghanistan while containing the military campaign against the Taliban insurgency (Garamone, 2017). Based on the new strategy, the US military deployed 25,000 additional troops, 4,000 of whom were to train the Afghan National Army and Afghan National Police. The administration hoped that this new strategy would curb the increasing violence in Afghanistan by showing that the war was now a high priority of the US.

During Obama’s presidency, the United States government had taken several measures to hold peace talks with several Afghan-Taliban leaders with the goal of ending the war in Afghanistan. No significant breakthroughs were achieved. In early 2011, after years of preparing a new peace deal, the United States under the then Secretary of State Hilary Clinton, presented what appeared to be an unambiguous policy of pursuing peace negotiations. The content of the secret negotiations between the Taliban representatives and U.S. officials that started in late 2010, was framed to allow the Taliban break with Al Qaeda, renounce violence, and abide by the Afghan constitution. The talks were aimed at measures for building confidence of the Taliban, especially in the issues of prisoner exchange and the opening of a Taliban political office in Doha, Qatar (Driscoll, 2014).

It has always been obvious that an apparent victory for the United States and its Afghan allies was not feasible. The US has been on the ground and directly involved in the 18-year old war that analysts have described as stalemate. Although al-Qaeda in Afghanistan and Pakistan are now considered to be “diminished”, the war with the Taliban insurgents rages on. Ending the 18-year conflict has eluded former US presidents and Donald Trump on assumption of office considered the war too costly. Similarities with the process to end the Vietnam War - America's longest war prior to 2010 - have been noted, which resulted in the Paris Peace Accords in 1973 (Yahaya, 2020).

The President Donald Trump’s new strategy for Afghanistan was unveiled in August 2017. According to President Trump, it is “counterproductive...to announce in advance the dates we intend to begin, or end, military options.” (Ahmad, 2019). He further emphasized that “we will not talk about number of troops or our plans for further military activities. The President Trump speech widened the scope of the American strategy wherein he referred to a ‘Political Settlement’ as an outcome of ‘Effective Military Effort’ but could not explain the US goals and conditions for the putative political process in Afghanistan. But after a period of a few months, the US administration focused on entering into parley with the Taliban, while

ignoring the government of Afghanistan or any of its nominees (Thomas, 2020). It was not a good decision to ignore the Afghan government in the talks since the basic issue is between the Afghan government and the Taliban but President Trump soon realized participation of the Afghan government is *sine qua non* to the agreement. The reversed approach by the US administration, centered around an “Afghan-led, Afghan-owned reconciliation process” that resulted in the US-Taliban direct parley occurring in July 2018 in Doha, Qatar (Marshall, 2019). Nonetheless, the United States did not pursue a fully negotiated political settlement until 2019 under the Donald Trump led administration.

In a four-page document, the government of the United States of America signed a peace accord with the Taliban movement to end the decade old war in Afghanistan. In summary, the agreement, which is officially titled “Agreement for Bringing Peace to Afghanistan between the Islamic Emirate of Afghanistan which is not recognized by the United States as a state and is known as the Taliban and the United States of America”, is made up of four parts which essentially summarizes that the United States is committed to withdraw from Afghanistan all military forces of the United States, its allies, and coalition partners, including all non-diplomatic civilian personnel, private security contractors, trainers, advisors, and supporting services personnel. In turn the Islamic Emirate of Afghanistan which is not recognized by the United States as a nation state but as the Taliban shall ensure that none of its members, individuals or groups, more especially the al-Qaida, shall use Afghan soil to threaten the security of the United States and its allies. Furthermore, a clear message will be sent that those who pose a threat to the United States and its allies have no place in Afghanistan and measures will be taken to prevent any group from taking such measures that pose any threat to the United States and its allies. The essence of this academic project is to investigate and assess the Trump’s administration’s peace deal with Afghan-Taliban leaders and also measure its success or failure in engendering peace and stability in Afghanistan.

Statement of the Research Problem

The Afghan-Taliban war rippled the Afghanistan economy. The war affected USA economic and political interest with Afghanistan. The successive US governments of the George Bush, Bill Clinton, and Barack Obama, before the Donald Trump’s administration had failed to commence viable peace deal with the Taliban. The policy of “kill and capture” and “state-building” had not yielded the desired effect of bringing about peace and stability of Afghanistan as the Taliban continued its insurgency. Trump’s engagement with the Taliban led to the signing of the peace deal.

The peace deal was intended as a launch pad for a negotiate end to Afghan war and stability in the country. But the negotiation and the deal itself has its critics and proponents. The focus of the debate was the capacity of the deal to achieve the ultimate objective of bringing peace and stability in Afghanistan. This is the context in which this work seeks to critically interrogate the context and content of the peace deal with a view to establishing the capacity or otherwise to bring about peace and stability in the war torn country.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Review

Armed Conflict

The concept of conflict as a feature of human society is as old as mankind. Conflict is state of disagreement or hostility between two or more people (Nicholson, 1992). By this, it means two or more parties do not have an accord and are as such on two different parallels on the same issue. It thus suggests the pursuit of incompatible goals. Put differently, conflict means collision course; it also refers to opposition to existing view, stand, or position.

In politics, conflict is more explicitly defined. Conflict is said to exist when two or more groups engage in a struggle over values and claims to status, power and resources in which the aims of the opponents are to neutralize, injure or eliminate the rivals (Idigo, 2024). Conflict is a demonstration of cross-purposes of distinct or similar political groups which often ends in political violence, and political violence, when contextualized in the Weberian sense, according to Anifowose (1982), is an acceptable weapon to ventilate anger.

Goal incompatibility implies opposing or diametrically opposed motives or pursuits. Conflict also connotes different perceptions, which may not necessarily result in hostility. This way, conflict simply means ‘a different perception’ or view to an issue or situation (Barash & Webel, 2002). Here, it may mean a different interpretation of a motive, or a different world-view. These include religion, customs, cosmologies or values. Such differences may never culminate in direct and sharp confrontations. On the other hand however, different perceptions, values or world-views may transcend just ‘differences’ and result in the extreme connotation of conflict. Inter-faith violence is a critical example of such breakdown. This means that conflicts can be armed and non-armed.

The term armed conflict found its place in the international dictionary for the first time in 1946 during the Conference of the National Red Cross (Elder, 1979). Armed conflict can be defined in the narrow and broad sense. Armed conflicts in the narrow sense mean the use of the armed forces by one or more states against another state or group of states with a view to imposing their own will to them – attacked countries (Sakan, 2003 cited in Petrović, Kankaraš & Cvetković, 2016). It represents the military – technological social phenomenon, in which the mutual destruction of two or more adversaries in the conflict fulfil political, economic, military, diplomatic or confessional objectives of the conflicting adversaries, which could not be achieved by other activities (Petrović, Cvetković & Stojiljković, 2015).

In a broader sense, armed conflict means any use of the armed forces, whether it comes to the engagement of one state or group of states against another state or group of states with a view to imposing their own will, or that it is an internal conflict (rebellion or revolution) or ‘border incidents in which a firearm is used and the armed forces deployed (Sakan, 2003, cited in Petrović, Kankaraš & Cvetković, 2016).

It involves a fight between or among groups with the use of weapons that can cause destruction of lives and property, and massive turmoil. According to the Amnesty International (July 2021), “Armed conflicts has continued to cause death, displacement and suffering on a massive scale around the world. Numerous armed conflicts are currently taking place around the world including those involving warring parties within a single state (non-international armed conflicts) and those involving armed forces from two or more states (international armed conflicts).

Peace and Peace Process

Literally, the word “peace” is derived from the original Latin word “pax”, which means a pact, a control or an agreement to end war or any dispute and conflict between two people, two nations or two antagonistic groups of people (Khemando, 1995). The US Militaries see peace mostly as an absence of war (Shinwari, 2019). This is because in the history of human society, wars of various kinds were fought. Whenever wars occur, people need peace and ask for peace. Peace that people needed and asked for is the state of the absence of wars, the state of having no fights.

In the view of Albert Einstein, the definition of Peace is beyond an absence of war. This connotes that peace is not only an absence of war, but it means or includes the presence of justice, law, order or government in the society. Aptly put, “Peace is not merely the absence of war but the presence of justice, of law, of order – in short, of government” (Vesilind, 2005). Hence peace is the presence of government regulations and administration of justice that ensures absence of fighting and acrimony. The attainment of peace takes the route of peace process. A generic definition of peace process includes a wide range of activities from a ceasefire achieved by negotiations, signing of peace agreements, disarmament, demobilization and rehabilitation of former combatants to nation-building.

Peace processes can be categorized into two stages. The first stage is the cessation of conflict, and the second stage is peace building. The first stage can be further grouped into negotiations and cessation of hostilities, while the second is composed of transition and consolidation phases (Ball, 2001). There are two possible means to kick-starting a peace processes. The first is the facilitation of a peace process by external actors, and for conflict affected countries accepting and working with the external mediations. The second way is a more proactive approach that peace processes are initiated by local stakeholders

without external assistance. There are no studies that has been done to explain whether the means for initiating a peace process has correlation with the success or failure.

Peace building

Peace building is part of peace process. It is a long-term process that occurs after violent conflict has slowed down or come to a halt. The United Nations (UN) document titled *An Agenda for Peace*, refers to peace building as a wide range of activities associated with capacity building, reconciliation, and societal transformation (Boutros-Ghali, 1995). Peace building involves a range of measures targeted to reduce the risk of lapsing or relapsing into conflict by strengthening national capacities at all levels for conflict management, and to lay the foundations for sustainable peace and sustainable development. (UN, 2007).

This consists of a set of physical, social, and structural initiatives that are often an integral part of post-conflict reconstruction and rehabilitation.

It revolves around the act of finding the ways and means to quell crisis, and bring an end to war. This demands the understanding of the cause(s) of the conflict and solving it (them). In the view of Conciliation Resource (2021), Peace building is a process that seeks to address the underlying causes of conflict, helping people to resolve their differences peacefully and lay the foundations to prevent future violence. This often entail a long-term process of encouraging people to talk, repair relationships, and reform institutions. This process can take numerous series of different actions that aims to bring different groups together, either to a physical meeting or through an electronic media, to discuss the issues, in order to understand the viewpoints of others.

In a narrower sense, peace building is a process that facilitates the establishment of durable peace and tries to prevent the recurrence of violence by addressing root causes and effects of conflict through reconciliation, institution building, and political as well as economic transformation (Boutros-Ghali, 1995).

It is generally agreed that the central task of peace building is to create positive peace, a "stable social equilibrium in which the surfacing of new disputes does not escalate into violence and war." (Maiese, 2003). Sustainable peace is characterized by the absence of physical and structural violence, the elimination of discrimination, and self-sustainability (Reychler, 2001). Moving towards this sort of environment goes beyond problem solving or conflict management. Peace building initiatives try to fix the core problems that underlie the conflict and change the patterns of interaction of the involved parties (Reychler, 2001). They aim to move a given population from a condition of extreme vulnerability and dependency to one of self-sufficiency and well-being (Lederach, 1997).

Peace building measures also aim to prevent conflict from re-emerging. Through the creation of mechanisms that enhance cooperation and dialogue among different identity groups, these measures can help parties manage their conflict of interests through peaceful means. This might include building institutions that provide procedures and mechanisms for effectively handling and resolving conflict (Maiese, 2003). For example, societies can build fair courts, capacities for labour negotiation, systems of civil society reconciliation, and a stable electoral process (Doyle & Sambanis, 2001). Such designing of new dispute resolution systems is an important part of creating a lasting peace.

The methods included in peace building vary depending on the situation and the agent of peace building. Successful peace building activities create an environment supportive of self-sustaining, durable peace; reconcile opponents; prevent conflict from restarting; integrate civil society; create rule of law mechanisms; and address underlying structural and societal issues. Researchers and practitioners also increasingly find that peace building is most effective and durable when it relies upon local conceptions of peace and the underlying dynamics that foster or enable conflict (Coning, 2013).

The Taliban

The Taliban is a movement of religious students (talib) from the Pashtun areas of eastern and southern Afghanistan who were educated in traditional Islamic schools. The group emerged in Afghanistan in the mid-1990s following the withdrawal of Soviet troops, the collapse of Afghanistan's communist regime,

and the subsequent breakdown in civil order. According to the Britannica (2022), Taliban was formed by Afghan mujahideen, or Islamic guerilla fighters, who had resisted the Soviet occupation of Afghanistan (1979–89) with the covert backing of the CIA and its Pakistani counterpart, the Inter-Services Intelligence directorate (ISI). It began as a small force of Afghan religious students and scholars seeking to confront crime and corruption (Maizland, 2021).

The emergence of Taliban was an aftermath of the failure of the Afghanistan government to establish civil order. The masses were subjected to frequent extortion and assault from local militias and warlords. Many Afghans, haven faced with mass displacement during the war, gave solidarity to the mujahideen in schools of Islamic sciences (called madrasahs) in southern Afghanistan and northern Pakistan. In 1994 a group of former fighters, associated with a madrasah in a village of Kandahār province, successfully subdued a local warlord and began pacifying nearby areas. The faction, which enjoyed popular support with its promise of security and its religious fervour, quickly grew into the movement now known as the Taliban. By late 1996 the Taliban had seized the capital, Kabul, and gained effective control over some two-thirds of the country.

The ideology of the Taliban was against the Western culture and system of governance. The Taliban came into power and asserted its own interpretation of law and order. It combined a strict religious ideology - a mixture of Deobandi traditionalism and Wahhābī puritanism - with a conservative Pashtun social code (Pashtunwali) to create a brutally repressive regime (Maizland, 2021). Its policies included the near-total exclusion of women from public life (including employment and education), the systematic destruction of non-Islamic artistic relics (as occurred in the town of Bamiyan), and the implementation of harsh criminal punishments. Taliban jurisprudence was drawn from the Pashtuns' pre-Islamic tribal code and interpretations of sharia coloured by the austere Wahhabi doctrines of the madrassas' Saudi benefactors. The regime neglected social services and other basic state functions. The Ministry for the Promotion of Virtue and Prevention of Vice even required women to wear the head-to-toe burqa, or *chadri*. There was total ban on music and television. All men were demanded to have beard and a jail is extended to men whose beards was deemed too short.

The Taliban regime collapsed after the invasion of the US in 2001. The Taliban was accused of providing a sanctuary to Osama Bin Laden in addition to the AL Qaeda movement (Hirsh, 2019). Despite the huge numbers of foreign troops, the Taliban regained their influence, and the violence level increased. The attacks from Taliban grew unabated between 2002 and 2006; by late 2007 Afghanistan snowballed into "serious danger" and war broke out. The Taliban returned to power in 2021 after regrouping in Pakistan and waging an insurgency against the U.S.-backed government in Kabul. The group faces the challenges of forming a functioning government and providing health services and economic opportunities to Afghans.

THE AFGHAN WAR

Terror and the US Global War on Terrorism

Throughout its history, Afghanistan has been a theatre of war. Of interest to us is the most recent by Taliban waged with the Afghanistan governance for twenty years from 2001 to 2021. The war was an aftermath of the September 11, 2001 attack on the US Pentagon and World Trade Centre suspected by the US government to be masterminded on AL Qaeda led by Osama Bin Laden. The Taliban provided refuge to AL Qaeda and refused to hand over Osama Bin Laden.

The war started on October 2001 following the U.S.-led invasion that toppled the original regime. According to the US president George W. Bush mission was to "disrupt the use of Afghanistan as a terrorist base of operations and to attack the military capability of the Taliban regime." The US forces ousted the Taliban, and the Taliban retreated to Pakistan (Tariq, 2020). The Taliban continued to wage an insurgency against the government in Kabul from Pakistan. Both the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) and the US worked to support the Kabul government's authority in addition to fighting the Taliban insurgency. According to the Maizland (2021), Taliban began taking back territory less than ten years after their ouster.

NATO forces ended their combat mission in 2014 because the US ordered so and the security responsibilities passed to the Afghan army and police, but around seventeen thousand NATO troops and that including US service members remained and the reason is to train, advise and assist Afghan security forces in the country.

The Afghan war recorded a huge loss in resources and human lives. It recorded about 157,000 death, including 43,000 civilians (Yahaya, 2020). As at 2018, there were over 2.5 million Afghan refugees. According to the Americans, there were 2,400 killed and 20,000 injured in addition to over 1,100 NATO troops that died. Also, 45,000 Afghan troops and police officers were killed. Moreover, the war cost Americans around \$2 trillion. Also, billions of dollars was spent on medical and care for American veterans (Merrills, 2018). The war supported the proliferation of terrorism in the world. The fierce resistance from the Taliban was a result of supports from some terrorist cartels (Merrills, 2018).

Actors and Interest in the Afghan War

The principal actors to the Afghan war are the Taliban and the Afghanistan government. The USA and others including Pakistan, Iran, India and Russia as well as NATO share interests in the Afghan war. The core interest of the Taliban was to gain international recognition as a legitimate political actor, remove their key leaders from the UN terrorist lists, and release of some prisoners. It also sought to re-establish the Emirate of Islamic law and purge Afghanistan of corrupt government leaders and prosecute the unfriendly warlords.

To the Afghanistan Government, the key interest was to remain in power they introduce democratic governance tenure. The government sought to provide security for Karzai, his family, and inner circle and immunity for some key allies. The government also planned for an orderly and phased withdrawal of the International Security Assistance Force (ISAF) and U.S. forces with continued training and weapons. Consequently it sought to establish a sustainable power-sharing with non-Pashtun elements to forestall a civil war on sectarian lines. The government of Karzai envisaged to gain continued international financial support, it is able to enthrone a democratic Afghanistan with the current constitution largely preserved and some new minority and civil protections.

The Pakistani interests include to ensure a neutral, stable Kabul government with the Afghan Taliban as a junior partner (Pickering, 2011). The Pakistan is at competition with India on keeping bilateral relations with Afghanistan. The key economic interest of the Pakistani was to limit the Indian influence, including effective checks on aid to the Baloch insurgency expanding trade and investment in Afghanistan.

The U.S.A's interests was to prevent the resurgence of al Qaeda in Afghanistan, and assist in maintaining a reasonable stable, friendly, autonomous Afghanistan. This way the US would ensure preservation of democratic and human rights in Afghanistan. The interest in maintaining the credibility of NATO was also held high, as NATO serves as the police of the world in reducing illicit drug trade and related world crime.

The Indian was relatively neutral in the war as it only wanted an Afghanistan not dominated by the Taliban or other Pakistan proxies. Their interest in the war was to eliminate al Qaeda and other Islamic extremists who target India. This will enable them to expand their trade and investment, including transit routes through Pakistan. The alliance was also to strengthen their growing strategic partnership with the United States.

The interest of the Iran in the Afghan was to see to the withdrawal of U.S. and ISAF military and intelligence forces. They wanted a stable regime in Kabul that is friendly to Iran, and not dominated by Pakistan or its proxies. This is expected to bolster the Iranian economic interest in trade, investment, and transit trade through Char Bahar. The Iranian government understands that peace in Afghanistan will lead to a return of 2 to 3 million Afghan refugees in Iran; and as well lead to the reduction/elimination of narcotics trafficking that ravage the Iranian society.

According to Pickering (2011), many of the interests of the parties to the Afghanistan civil war seem to overlap. All seem to desire to end the war, including the Taliban, Karzai government, the Pakistani, the US government, the Indian, and the Iran. The presence of many areas of overlapping interest brought the prospect for the negotiation of peace agreement to end the war in Afghanistan.

The USA – Taliban Peace Diplomacy

The Negotiation Process

In Pickering (2011), Negotiations were not included in the strategic mix of dealing with Afghanistan or, for that matter, Iraq under the George W. Bush administration. One can only conjecture about reasons. They may have included a sense that a military victory was possible; a belief that talk about negotiations was in itself a sign of weakness that should not—and could not—be conveyed to the opponent; full-blown distrust of the Taliban; a need to have a better balance of forces and more success behind us before we took on the task; a hope that a reintegration process, together with raising the military stakes, would be sufficient to win the day; and a distrust of diplomats and politicians who might be expected to conduct the negotiations - a sense that all achieved with the expenditure of so much blood and treasure would be given away if diplomats and politicians were turned loose on the problem.

While the administration policy of President Barack Obama regarding Afghanistan negotiations does not represent a radical departure from that of its predecessor, there has been greater openness to debate prospects and issues, and a sense that an unofficial effort at the proper time could have a useful and positive impact on the interest in negotiations as well as setting out the problems to be undertaken and overcome to achieve success in them”. (Century foundation report, 2011).

When Donald Trump was inaugurated as president, he seemed determined to end the longest war in U.S. history. Unlike Obama, Trump, as a presidential candidate, was critical of U.S. involvement in Afghanistan. On the campaign trail, Trump repeatedly called invading Afghanistan a “terrible mistake” because it was “a complete waste of lives and money” (Johnson 2017).

President Trump’s approach to counterterrorism was in obvious contrast to his predecessor’s approach, resembling more of President Bush’s policy direction on terrorism, President Trump advocated that the United States should focus more on the pursuit of its own interests in Afghanistan and abandon the notion that democracy can be exported into another country.

President Trump’s decision to maintain a military presence in Afghanistan and send reinforcements to the country was not a strategy for victory (Brown, 2017: 1); it was seen as a strategy of delay with hopes that the continuous onslaught would force the Taliban to the negotiation table. Indeed, by late 2017, the U.S. and its allies have abandoned their hopes of a military victory over the Taliban insurgency in Afghanistan. The American public’s opinion of the War in Afghanistan stabilized in most polls. The findings of a 2018 poll by the Koch Institute suggested that 57% of Americans supported President Trump’s authorization of the withdrawal of all U.S. troops from Afghanistan, whereas 19% of Americans opposed it (Kristian, 2019).

The same poll also revealed that only 33% of Americans were in favor of negotiation with the Taliban to end the war, whereas 37% of Americans were opposed to talks between the U.S. and the Taliban. In October 2018, the findings of the Pew Research Center survey also demonstrated that Americans remained pessimistic about the U.S. approach in Afghanistan, with 49% of respondents stating that the U.S. had failed to accomplish its goals and 35% saying that the U.S. was successful in accomplishing its goals in Afghanistan. (Rasouli, 2020). The negotiating team was formed without the inclusion of the officials of the Afghan government. The agreement was negotiated on behalf of the US government by Zalmay Mamozy Khalilzad who was an Afghan-American diplomat and foreign policy expert. The deal had secret annexes and was instrumental to the collapse of the Afghan National Security Forces (Borger, 2022).

Withdrawing the United States military presence from Afghanistan has always being the one specific goal of the Trump administration. The flaw in this strategy is that the Taliban has made very modest concessions in the talks because its leaders understand that the Americans are leaving, so they see themselves as the inevitable and imminent victors. The losing party in this strategy is the Afghan government, which feels abandoned by its American partner. (Rosouli, 2020).

There are no guarantees that this peace agreement will end all forms of insurgency rather we are likely to see an escalation of violence due to the fracturing of the Taliban leadership and the non-involvement of the Kabul led Afghan Government. However, overall, the Taliban negotiation agenda seems clear: the

Taliban leadership have separated their negotiations into two different tracks. The first is with the U.S. over the withdrawal and, if that is agreed, the second is with Afghan political groups other than the Afghan government over the future of governance in Afghanistan (Rosouli, 2020). It seems that the Trump administration considers unconditional peace talks with the Taliban to be a “potentially disastrous” but necessary endeavor to end the United States’ longest war with minimal embarrassment (Lieven, 2019). Thus, in February 2020, after rounds of discussions, the negotiators’ peace, signed the peace agreement.

The terms and condition of the Afghan peace agreement

Towards ending the war in Afghanistan a peace agreement was signed between the Taliban and the USA. The agreement titled an Agreement for Bringing Peace to Afghanistan was consented to on February 29, 2020, in Doha, Qatar (*Qazi, 2020*). The four pillars of the agreement are ceasefire, withdrawal of foreign troops, *intra-Afghan negotiations and Counterterrorism assurances* (Maizland, 2020).

In the Cease-fire content of the Doha agreement, the negotiators agreed to atemporary reduction in violence and said that a lasting cease-fire among U.S., Taliban, and Afghan forces will be part of intra-Afghan negotiations.

Another major issue to the agreement was the withdrawal of foreign forces wherein the United States agreed to reduce its number of troops in the country from roughly 12,000 to 8,600 within 135 days. If the Taliban follows through on its commitments, all U.S. and other foreign troops will leave Afghanistan within fourteen months.

The third issue agreed to is an *Intra-Afghan negotiations*. The Taliban agreed to start talks with the Afghan government. The intra-Afghan negotiations was scheduled to begin on 10th March, 2020 in Oslo Norway (*Gannon & Lee, 2020*). Throughout the negotiating process, the Taliban had resisted direct talks with the government, calling it an American puppet. But the Taliban has more recently indicated that talks are possible, with deputy Taliban leader Sirajuddin Haqqani writing in a *New York Times* op-ed, “If we can reach an agreement with a foreign enemy, we must be able to resolve intra-Afghan disagreements through talks.”

The deal requires the Afghan government to release 5,000 Taliban prisoners by the start of the talks, in a prisoner exchange for 1,000 government soldiers held by the Taliban (*Graham-Harrison, Sabbagh, Akhtar & Berger, 2020*). The Afghan government was not a party to the deal, and on March 1 Ghani stated that he would reject the prisoner exchange: "The government of Afghanistan has made no commitment to free 5,000 Taliban prisoners. The release of prisoners is not the United States authority, but it is the authority of the government of Afghanistan (*Schuknecht, 2020*). Both parties accepted to go into internal negotiation but disagreed on the status of the release of the prisoners in the negotiation process. While Ghani averred that any prisoner exchange "cannot be a prerequisite for talks," but must be a part of the negotiations the Taliban stated that they were "fully ready" for the intra-Afghan talks, but that there would be no talks if about 5,000 of their prisoners are not released. He also said that the agreed-upon period of reduction in violence was over and that operations against Afghan government forces could resume (*Sediqi, 2020; BBC News, 2020*).

The intra-Afghan negotiations did not begin as planned on March 10, 2020. However, on that day Ghani signed a decree ordering the Afghan government to start releasing 1,500 Taliban prisoners on March 14 if they agreed to sign pledges guaranteeing they will not return to battle (*Shalizi, 2020*). If they do not sign the pledges, the decree will not go into effect (*Shalizi, 2020*). The same day, the U.S. started withdrawing some troops (*Snow, 2020*). *After series of doubts and cautions, the Afghan government freed about 5,000 Taliban prisoners as contained in the Doha agreement as requested by the Trump administration. The Afghan Peace Negotiations (APN) between the Afghan government and the Taliban did not involve any third-party beyond hosting and supporting roles (Smith, 2021).*

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Advanced Training Program on Humanitarian Action (ATHA) (2018) in a review of the humanitarian, political, societal, and economic dimensions that make the protracted conflict in Afghanistan intractable and precarious for civilian populations. The report is based on field visits to numerous regions in Afghanistan in July 2018—which included interviews and consultations with a variety of actors, including political stakeholders, humanitarian agencies, and populations affected by conflict—as well as a review of recent and relevant literature. The study aimed to provide a current assessment of the conflict, drawing from field interviews and an in-depth assemblage of various reports and resources, and examine the interconnected and interdependent interests fuelling the conflict. The findings showed that “The U.S. government greatly overestimated its ability to build and reform government institutions in Afghanistan as part of the stabilization strategy,” and that “under immense pressure to quickly stabilize insecure districts, U.S. government agencies spent far too much money, far too quickly, and in a country woefully unprepared to absorb it.”

Ahmed (2017) the USA strategy to ending the war and maintain peace in Afghanistan was the use of state-building process. This study discussed the impact of the Taliban’s exclusion from both Bonn Conferences (2001 and 2011) on Afghanistan’s state-building process and prolonged humanitarian disaster consequences. It used the qualitative method of research. The review outlined the challenges faced by the democratic institutions of Afghanistan due to the non-recognition and exclusionist policies adopted by the United States and its partner forces to include rampant insecurity, endemic corruption, Illicit Narcotics and weak governance. Two hypotheses developed for the study were tested and showed that the United States and its coalition forces misperceived the imperatives of stability in Afghanistan, and that the exclusion of the Taliban from the Bonn Conference sowed the first seeds of long lasting insurgency and re-emergence of the Taliban. The study concluded that negotiation and peace talks among confronting parties is the panacea to the ongoing human atrocities in Afghanistan.

Miller and Blake (2019) x-rayed the peace process between the USA and Taliban movement towards the ending of the civil war in Afghanistan. The study noted that there had been series of failed attempts to beginning negotiating to end to the war in Afghanistan. It was observed that the prospects of the latest peace process that gained momentum in 2019, but the visions of the parties to political settlement remained obscure and underdeveloped. The study employed three sources to data collection which includes published material describing the interests and probable goals of the conflict parties related to a potential peace process, past peace agreements, both for Afghanistan and for many other countries around the world, and in-person confidential consultations, primarily during the second half of 2018, with approximately 85 individuals. The findings of the study revealed the possible outcome of the negotiations to include that Power-sharing could exacerbate Afghanistan’s political fragility, Clear-enough transitional security arrangements will be tough to achieve, implementation probably will not be guaranteed by a peace keeping or peace enforcement mission, spoilers on all sides will need to be contained, transitional government and security arrangements could become stuck, and that Afghanistan will remain vulnerable to the effects of contestation between external actors.

Yahaya (2020) employed the qualitative research technique to emerging conflicts or peace initiative in the peace movement in Afghanistan. The study noted that the Afghan peace process entails the proposals and the negotiations embodied in the bid to end the ongoing war in Afghanistan. The study revealed that the negotiations to the peace movement intensified in 2018 amid talks between the Taliban, and American troops. The study found that a mutual agreement between the Taliban and the United States is expected to follow a phased American withdrawal and the start of intra-Afghan peace talks. In addition, the study saw that aside from the United States, Afghanistan's neighbours Pakistan, China and India, as well as Russia, play a part in facilitating the peace process. It was agreed that the present peace deal between Taliban and USA is the "more productive than they have been in the past" to end the Afghan civil war. The content is the withdrawal of US and international troops from Afghanistan and the Taliban not allowing other jihadist groups to operate within the country. The study was of the opinion that a sustainable peace in Afghanistan demands justice, fair play among the conflicting parties and that the US government must

value the culture, and tradition of Afghanistan as well as look at the Taliban group demand and works with Afghanistan government to bring peace and end conflict in the Afghanistan.

Farr (2020) examined the Afghan peace agreement and the associated problems. It found that the recently agreed truce between the USA and Taliban of the February 29, 2020, in Doha, Qatar contains largely the same conditions that had been agreed upon in September 2019 but which was scuttled by President Donald Trump. It revealed that the content of the agreement were the removal of United States and Coalition forces from Afghanistan in exchange for the promise that the Taliban would not allow terrorist groups to operate on Afghan soil. However, the agreement is premised on several assumptions that will make its success problematic. The agreement assumes a functioning Afghan government in Kabul with which to negotiate. The Afghan presidential election conducted amid the negotiation, rather than resolving who is in charge, was part of the muddied waters to the failed presidential election took place in September 2019. The vote counting process was so confused and contested that the winner was not announced until February 18, 2020, which was almost five months after the election took place. The flawed and contentious election resulted in a contested and split government in Kabul, creating a stalemate regarding who is in charge and making the implementation of the next step in the peace agreement problematic. The result may be that with a weak, or split, government in Kabul, the Taliban will be in a stronger position to dictate terms of an agreement over the future of Afghanistan favourable to their point of view. But the Taliban had its own leadership problems: the study further found that the team negotiating the peace agreement in Doha does not necessarily speak for the Taliban commanders in the field, who may not be willing, or able, to give up the fight and lay down their arms. This leaves the possibility of continued fighting even after a deal in Kabul is reached.

Tariq (2020) examined US-Taliban talks in the context of intra-Afghan talks. The key aims of the agreement was to provide for the restoration of peace in Afghanistan and withdrawal of the US troops from Afghanistan after a period of about 19 years. It also provides for the swap of 5,000 Taliban held by the government and 1,000 Afghan in the custody of Taliban. The agreement cannot be put into practice on account of mutual distrust by both the Afghan government and the Taliban. The study posits that the US government is under pressure to resume talks with Taliban as the government of Afghanistan is constantly faced with the threat of insurgency from Taliban, the ISKP or ISIS. The conclusion was that the US withdrawal from Afghanistan and failure of the US-Taliban is the proof that the theory of realism has been proven insufficient to shape the politics of the smaller states.

Rasouli (2020) examined the roles of the U.S. to achieve some level of reconciliation with the Taliban after more than 18 years of war in Afghanistan. The study traced the history of U.S.-Taliban negotiations and the U.S. initiatives to engage with the Taliban, as well as outlining the challenges to these initiatives and determining how effective they have been. In addition, the prospects of the U.S.-Taliban peace talks are assessed. Since the 2001 U.S. intervention in Afghanistan, the first two U.S. administrations under consideration—those of George W. Bush and Barack Obama—justified intrusive interventions into the political, economic, and social affairs of Afghanistan under a “state-building” approach to address a combination of security and humanitarian challenges. The U.S. promoted state-building initiatives guided by a liberal peace-building ideology that were supposed to promote peace, democracy, and market-led development in the region. Two years after Trump came to office, his administration abandoned this state-building approach and hopes of a military victory over the Taliban insurgency in Afghanistan. The qualitative study found that the process of peace talks between the U.S. and the Taliban lacked transparency and a clear strategy. Thus, it posited that the U.S. peace deal with the Taliban is more likely to create the conditions for future civil war than a sustainable peace among Afghans.

Chaudhuri and Shende (2020) assessed the risks associated with the February 29, 2020, United States and the Taliban peace agreement that marked a milestone in America’s longest ever war. The qualitative study noted that two key items of actions to the truce were that the majority of U.S. troops are expected to withdraw from Afghanistan by the end of 2021, and in turn the Taliban should play a larger role in Afghan politics as well as ensure that terrorism is managed in Afghanistan. The study further reviewed that role of India and Pakistan in the peace process in Afghanistan. Indian interest is their investments in

Afghanistan which may not be safe if the Haqqani group as a major Taliban faction, takes over power. The study identified the risks to the agreement to include terrorism, the growing influence of Pakistan's inter-services intelligence directorate, and increasing political instability in Kabul. The study discussed that solutions to these risks are broader diplomatic engagement, continued training and investment, and working with and through others.

Gap in Literature

The study has shown that there are some unfulfilled and gray areas in the context of the Afghan government and Taliban arms struggle under the Trump's administration and its capacity to engender peace in Afghanistan. The ceasefire agreement was initiated, negotiated and signed by the Trump's administration. The Biden administration did not support the appreciate the decision and blamed the Trump's administration for the actions that led to the withdrawal of troops from Afghanistan.

The extant literature had not succinctly discussed and appreciated the origin and evolution of the Afghan conflict, the US – Taliban peace deal, and the challenges facing the deal. These areas will be properly evaluated in this study. The need to explicate these are the crux of this study.

METHODOLOGY

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework is hinged on the hegemonic stability theory. The theory was developed in the 1970s to explain the Pax Britannica and the Pax Americana (Lake, 1993).

It was initiated by Charles P. Kindleberger with an argument that “states can only cooperate economically with one another when a hegemonic power holds the ring, economically or militarily” (Rosecrance, 1986). It posits that “when there is a strong dominant power, there will be stability, but when a strong power begins to slip and a new challenger rises, war is more likely” (Nye, 2000). In other word, a dominant actor with the necessary means is required for stability. There will be total chaos in the absence of such a hegemonic influence.

Although the theory applies to interstate relations and Taliban is not a state, it captures what played out in Afghanistan. The peace accord between USA and Taliban can guarantee peace as long as the USA (the hegemon) is there to guarantee the deal. The opposite, which is playing out, is that the abandonment by USA of its hegemonic role in Afghanistan unleashed chaos.

The research design that was employed for this study was the historical design.

This study applied the qualitative techniques of data analysis. The content analysis was relied upon. The method was used to determine the presence of certain words, themes or concepts within some given qualitative data (See Table 1). The method enabled the researcher to quantify and analyse the presence, meaning and relationship of the words, themes and concepts in Table 1 and based on them to draw inference about the study.

DATA ANALYSIS

USA - TALIBAN PEACE DEAL AND PROSPECTS OF PEACE IN AFGHANISTAN

The Process and Content of the Peace Deal

The Peace Deal is the Agreement for ending the Insurgence and bringing peace to Afghanistan that lasted for twenty years from 2001 to 2020. The peace deal is commonly known as the US–Taliban deal or the Doha Accords. The deal was an agreement between the USA and the Islamic Emirate of Afghanistan (known as the Taliban) which was not recognized by the United States as a state. On February 29, the U.S. envoy Khalilzad and the Taliban's Baradar signed an agreement (see Appendix 1) that paves the way for a significant draw-down of U.S. troops in Afghanistan and includes guarantees from the Taliban that the country will not be used for terrorist activities.

The peace process that ended the 20-year insurgence in Afghanistan was the process that followed from 2018 to 2021. Between April to June, 2018, the People's Peace Movement, held a peace march it called the “Helmand peace convey” that took them marching in protest from the Taliban-controlled territory to Kabul. The protest was a reaction of a car bombing on 23 March 2018 in Lashkar Gah that had killed 14

people. The protesters called for a ceasefire. In response to the protest, President Ashraf Ghani, on 5 June 2018, announced an unconditional ceasefire with the Taliban until 20 June, the end of Ramadan.

Following the reactions and protest from the masses, the US called for a negotiation with the Taliban government that was initiated in Doha in 2018. The Taliban set up a 21-man team to lead the negotiation, with the US envoy. The agreement had two phases. The first phase is the agreement between the US and Taliban; and the second phase is the Intra-Afghan dialogue and negotiations to consolidate the peace in Afghanistan.

The content of the US–Taliban agreement were called for prisoner exchange and the withdrawal of US forces. The deal led to the withdrawal of US forces from Afghanistan, the collapse of the Afghan Army, and the August 2021 Fall of Kabul to Taliban forces (*George, Ryan, Pager, Constable, Hudson, Witte, 2021*).

The intra-Afghan negotiations was to begin the following month, but Afghan President Ghani says the Taliban must meet his government's own conditions before it enters talks. The U.S.-Taliban deal doesn't call for an immediate cease-fire, and in the days after its signing, Taliban fighters carry out dozens of attacks on Afghan security forces. U.S. forces respond with an air strike against the Taliban in the southern province of Helmand.

The Peace Deal and Peace and Stability in Afghanistan

The aim of the USA-Taliban peace agreement processes was to return peace in Afghanistan and bring about social-economic stability to the country. The study aptly posed a research questions "Has the USA – Taliban deal the capacity to bring peace and stability in Afghanistan?"

To answer this question, the study x-rayed the incidences of the peace process to determine the eventual signing of the peace deal and existence of new government thereafter as the end product of the peace deal. The capacity to maintain peace and stability in Afghanistan is the extent of enforcement of the peace agreement with the core indicators of enforcement being cease-fire of the Taliban and withdrawal of military by the US.

The intention of the US for involvement in war with the Taliban was to bring peace and stability in Afghanistan. The US successive governments have pursued several policies aimed at returning peace and maintaining economic, social and political stability in Afghanistan. The Bush Administration started with the "War on Terror" to use coercion to end the terrorism in Afghanistan. The strategy was to kill or arrest the Taliban leaders and the Al Qaeda supporters as a means to gaining relative peace in the country. However, by 2003, administration officials had to change course toward policies that utilized liberal state-building as a result of ongoing violence, the discourses embedded in the "War on Terror," insurgency, and increasing recruitment among fundamentalist groups (Jenkins 2017). The critics that killed the policy of "war on terror" posit that the participating governments exploits it to pursue their own "long-standing policy/military objectives, reduce civil liberties, and infringe upon human rights" (*Singel, 2008; Richissin, 2004*). The change of strategy to the "state-building approach" was aimed to build institutions for social order and use them to launch civil rule and democratic governance in Afghanistan. The strategy saw the building of such liberal institutions as an independent Human Rights Commission, an independent Election Commission, and two chambers of parliament: the House of Representatives and the Senate (Rasouli, 2020). The strategy equally drove the Afghan government on social and economic policies that aimed to alter some of her social and religious orders. The US and western allies pressured the Afghan government into stopping buying fuel from Iran and changing some controversial religious laws, such as the "Shia Personal Status Law, and the Afghanistan's membership in the World Trade Organization (WTO). The state-building strategy created the atmosphere of apprehension and consensus among the Afghans that the Afghan government and parliament are not responding to domestic policymaking and are rather implementing an externally-driven agenda, rather than one that act independently and is driven by domestic interests (Cornish, 2014; Prashad, 2019).

It is a truism that the Donald Trump administration had a strategy to ending the war and conserving the US resource and personnel while retaining her reputation and economic interest in Afghanistan. The Peace Deal aimed to bring about cease-fire and return on peace and stability to Afghanistan. The deal was

for the US government to withdraw troops from Afghanistan by May 1, 2021, and a ceasefire from both the US and Taliban. The Taliban promise to halt attacks on Americans. However, they they stepped up attacks on Afghan government forces, who begin to fall apart with American tactical support now reduced. It is clear that the agreement did not abate the insurgency. The ceasefire offered by the Taliban was not to enable negotiation and end to the war but a temporary arrangement for the celebration of the Muslim religious holiday of Eid al-Adha, starting Friday, offering some respite from weeks of increasing violence. In the same year of the peace deal, it was reported that more than 1,280 Afghan civilians were being killed in the first six months of the year, from an ongoing fighting between Afghan government forces and the Taliban (Sediqi, 2020). The Taliban continued its operation until Aug. 15, 2021 when it captured Kabul, the capital city of Afghanistan and took over power from the Afghanistan government. The takeover of government brought about tension in the country as many Afghan citizens scrambled to flee the country as the U.S. troops and officials organize evacuation flights for them (Associated Press, 2022).

Sequel to the takeover, Afghanistan was plunged deeper into poverty due to international isolation and the economic upheaval (Amnesty International, 2022). The current situation in Afghanistan as reported by the Amnesty International (2022) is alarming and relatively uncommon of civil society. The report posit thus:

Restrictions on women's rights, freedom of the media and freedom of expression increased exponentially. Institutions designed to support human rights were severely limited or shut down completely. Peaceful protesters faced arbitrary arrests, torture and enforced disappearance. The Taliban conducted extrajudicial executions, arbitrary arrests, torture and unlawful detention of perceived opponents with impunity, creating an atmosphere of fear. Extreme poverty increased, exacerbated by drought and other natural disasters. Public executions and floggings were used as punishment for crimes such as murder, theft, "illegitimate" relationships or violating social norms. Women's rights continued to be attacked, and women's participation in public life was severely limited. Afghanistan was the only country in the world where girls were banned from attending secondary school. Almost all institutions set up to address gender-based violence under the former government were shut down by the Taliban.

The answer the research question is thus: there was a gradual withdrawal of troops by the US government which was expected to end by May 1 2021. However, the Taliban stop attacks on US troops and institutions in Afghanistan but refused to ceasefire on the war, until it captured the Capital of Afghanistan and took over government in 2021. This is to say that the peace deal did not brings about peace and stability in Afghanistan.

CONCLUSION

The peace deal between the US and Taliban brought a mixed picture. From the side of the US-Taliban peace deal, the agreed withdrawal of troops and cease-fire of attacks on US assets and interests, were well implemented. Thus the first phase of the agreement that covers the US interest was well accommodated to brings peace in Afghanistan. On the side of the Afghan government and Taliban peace talks to bring about lasting peace and stability was very arduous and complicated. The process, and number of prisonersto release, the system of governance to implement in Afghanistan and the level of reduction on violence by the Taliban were areas of disagreement that marred the intra-Afghan peace talks, and yet there was withdrawal of international assistance. The Deal exposed the Afghan government to helpless attacks and loss of the war and this erodes the ever sought peace and stability. The study thus posit that loss of sovereign power is detrimental to the peace of a nation State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The study advances the recommendations as follows:

1. A peace process that aims to protect the interest of the Masses and bring lasting peace and stability should be capable of integrating the all the parties in the peace deal. It is therefore recommended that taking the Afghanistan civil war as a case, the United Nations and any institution that seek peace for parties should consult all the stakeholders to the crisis. The USA-Taliban peace deal failed for lack of this. Thus, this study posit that any negotiation that is supposed to address conflict should always factor the aspiration of all the warring parties.
2. It is recommended that a sovereign nation with a legitimately constituted government must have a say in policies, and all agreements that will affects its existence of power in office. This study suggest thus that the USA isolation of the Afghan government in the peace deal with the Taliban is detrimental to the peace of the Afghanistan as a nation.
3. Parties that share vested interests in crises should not be part to the truce. This study recommends that neutrality should always be maintained in any peace process. The involvement of the USA which is the head of the United Nations portends vested interest. It is therefore recommended that parties to war, should step aside in any peace deal in a crisis situation.

REFERENCES

- ACLED (2020). The US-Taliban Peace Deal: 10 Weeks on 22 May 2020. Accessed on 20 April 2022, <https://acleddata.com/2020/05/22/the-us-taliban-peace-deal-10-weeks-on/>.
- Advanced Training Program on Humanitarian Action (ATHA) (2018). *Fragile Future: The human cost of conflict in Afghanistan*. Humanitarian Action at the Front-lines: Field Analysis Series. Harvard Humanitarian Initiative.
- Ahmad, J. S. (2019). An assessment of peace negotiations between the United States government and the Taliban insurgent group, 2001-2018. Research study submitted to Johns Hopkins University for the award of degree of Master of Arts in Global Security Studies.
- Ahmed, S. (2017). The exclusion of the Taliban from Afghanistan's state-building and its human security vulnerabilities. *IAFOR Journal of Politics, Economics & Law*, 4(1), 14 – 28.
- Amnesty International (2022). Afghanistan 2022. Accessed on 15 May 2022, from <https://www.amnesty.org/en/location/asia-and-the-pacific/south-asia/afghanistan/report-afghanistan/>
- Chaudhuri, R. & Shende, S. (2020). Dealing with the Taliban: India's strategy in Afghanistan after U.S. withdrawal. Working Paper of the Carnegie Endowment for International Peace. June 2020. Retrieved from https://carnegieendowment.org/files/Chaudhuri_Shende_-_Afghanistan.pdf.
- Conciliation Resources (2021). Peace building. Retrieved from <https://www.c-r.org/who-we-are/why-peacebuilding/what-peacebuilding>
- Farr, G. (2020). The Afghan peace agreement and its problems. April, 2020. Retrieved from <https://www.e-ir.info/2020/04/06/the-afghan-peace-agreement-and-its-problems>.
- Gannon, K. & Lee, M. (2020). "US and Taliban sign deal aimed at ending war in Afghanistan". Associated Press. Archived from the original on March 1, 2020. Retrieved from <https://web.archive.org/web/20200301032313/https://apnews.com/491544713df4879f399d0ff5523d369e>
- Garamone, J. (2017). President Unveils New Afghanistan, South Asia Strategy. Retrieved from <https://www.defense.gov/Explore/News/Article/Article/1284964/president-unveils-new-afghanistan-south-asia-strategy/>
- George, S., Ryan, M., Pager, T., Constable, P., Hudson, J., Witte, G. (2021). "Surprise, panic and fateful choices: The day America lost its longest war". The Washington Post. Retrieved from <https://www.washingtonpost.com/world/2021/08/28/taliban-takeover-kabul>.
- Graham-Harrison, E., Sabbagh, D. M., Akhtar, M. & Borger, J. (2020). "US and Taliban sign deal to withdraw American troops from Afghanistan". *The Guardian*. Retrieved

from <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2020/feb/29/us-taliban-sign-peace-agreement-afghanistan-war>

- Grant Farr (2020). The Afghan Peace Agreement and Its Problems <https://www.e-ir.info/2020/04/06/the-afghan-peace-agreement-and-its-problems/>
- Hirsh, M. (2019). *Ryan Crocker: The Taliban Will 'Retake the Country*. Retrieved from <https://foreignpolicy.com/2019/01/28/ryan-crocker-the-taliban-will-retake-the-country-afghanistan-deal/>
- Idigo(2025). African union, conflict resolution and Malian conflict: Multidisciplinary Research And Development Journal INT'L 7(1)2-23
- Idigo, B.C. (2022) Terrorism and national security in Nigeria: A case of Boko-Haram, 2019-2022. *International journal of general studies*, 2(1), pp. 86-104
- Idigo, B.C. (2024). Cross border migration and human security in Nigeria. *Journal of Education, Humanities, Management & Social Sciences*, (JEHMSS), 2(4), pp. 37-60 www.journalonline.com
- International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC) (2008). How is the Term "Armed Conflict" Defined in International Humanitarian Law? Opinion Paper, March 2008. blob: resource://pdf.js/cc61394d-52f5-4ca8-856a-2f029ae8a00a.
- Jenkins, B. (2017). Bush, Obama, And Trump: The Evolution of U.S. Counterterrorist Policy Since 9/11. Retrieved February 20, 2021, from <https://www.ict.org.il/Article/2079/BUSH-OBAMA-AND-TRUMP#gsc.tab=0>
- Jeong, H. (2000) *Peace and Conflict Studies: An Introduction*. Aldershot: Ashgate.
- Khan, A. (2016). Prospects of peace in Afghanistan. *Strategic Studies*. Pp 18 – 46. Retrieved from https://www.issi.org.pk/wp-content/uploads/2016/07/2-Amina_Khan_SS_Vol_36_No.1_2016.pdf.
- Khemanando, V. B. (1995). *Buddhism and Peace. Dictionary of Word Origins*, Calcutta: Lazo Print.
- Kriesberg, L. (2009) The evolution of conflict resolution. Retrieved from <https://www.maxwell.syr.edu/uploadedfiles/parcc/publications/2009%20evolution-conflictresolution.pdf>
- Kristian, B. (2019). Op-Ed: End Washington's stagnant Afghanistan war. Retrieved from <https://www.latimes.com/opinion/op-ed/la-oe-kristian-afghanistan-war-withdrawal-20190307-story.html>.
- Lake, D. (1993). British and American Hegemony compared: Lessons for the Current Era of Decline. In: Joseph M. Grieco (ed.) *The International System and the International Political Economy: Volume 1: Hegemony and Cooperation in the International Economy*. . Aldershot.
- Landler, M. (2017). The Afghan War and the Evolution of Obama. *The New York Times*. Retrieved February 20, 2021 from <https://www.nytimes.com/2017/01/01/world/asia/obama-afghanistan-war.html>
- Lederach, J. P. (1997). *Building Peace: Sustainable Reconciliation in Divided Societies*. Washington, D.C: United States Institute of Peace.
- Maiese, M. (2003). Peace building. *Beyond Intractability*. Guy Burgess & Heidi Burgess. Eds. *Conflict Information Consortium*, University of Colorado, Boulder. Posted: September 2003. Retrieved from <http://www.beyondintractability.org/essay/peacebuilding>.
- Maizland, L. (2020). U.S.-Taliban peace deal: What to know. March 2, 2020 3:00 pm. Retrieved from <https://www.cfr.org/backgrounder/us-taliban-peace-deal-agreement-afghanistan-war>.
- Maizland, L. (2021). The Taliban in Afghanistan. <https://www.cfr.org/backgrounder/taliban-afghanistan>
- Marshal, M. (2019). "U.S and Taliban Agree in Principle to Peace Framework. *New York Times*.
- Merrills, J. G. (2018). *International dispute settlement, negotiation*. University of Sheffield, Cambridge University Press, pp. 1-25 Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781316683149.002>.

- Miller, L. E. & Blake, J. S. (2019). Envisioning a comprehensive peace agreement for Afghanistan. Retrieved from https://www.rand.org/content/dam/rand/pubs/research_reports/RR2900/RR2937/RAND_RR2937.pdf.
- Nicholson, M. (1992) *Rationality and the Analysis of International Conflict*. Cambridge University Press.
- Niland, N. (2014). *Democratic Aspirations and Destabilizing Outcomes in Afghanistan*. Rhode Island, USA: Watson Institute
- Nye, J. (2000). *Understanding International Conflicts*. New York, Longman.
- O'Hanlon, M. E. (2020). from Chaos: On Afghanistan, give peace a chance — but be wary of the Taliban. Wednesday, March 4, 2020. <https://www.brookings.edu/blog/order-from-chaos/2020/03/04/on-afghanistan-give-peace-a-chance-but-be-wary-of-the-taliban/>
- Shalizi, H. (2020). "Exclusive: Afghan government to release 1,500 Taliban prisoners from jails - decree". Reuters. Retrieved <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-afghanistan-taliban-prisoners-decree/exclusive-afghan-government-to-release-1500-taliban-prisoners-from-jails-decree-idUSKBN20X30W>.
- Tariq, M. (2020). US-Afghan talks: Myths and realities. *Global Political Review*, V(I), 104-111. doi:10.31703/gpr.2020(V-I).12.
- Thomas, C. (2020). *Afghanistan: Background and U.S. Policy In Brief*. Congressional Research Service :<http://crsreports.congress.gov>.
- Vesilind, P. A. (2005). *Peace engineering: when personal values and engineering careers converge*, USA: Lakeshore Press. blob: resource://pdf.js/710cf731-6095-4038-b6f0-4bb9b40874f5
- Worden, S. (2020). U.S., Taliban Sign Historic Agreement—Now Comes the Hard Part: Can Afghans and the Taliban come together and forge a political settlement? Monday, March 2, 2020. <https://www.usip.org/publications/2020/03/us-taliban-sign-historic-agreement-now-comes-hard-part>
- Yahaya, J. U. (2020). Peace movement in Afghanistan: Emerging conflict or peace initiative. *African Scholar Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 17(6), 91 – 120.